

Case Images

Femoral Shaft Fracture Surgery with Ortho-Bridge System: A New Case Image

Liu Xue^{*}; Lee Zhang¹; Wang Xi^{1#}

1. Gannan Medical College, Ganzhou, Jianxi, China

^{*}Corresponding author: wangxi01@126.com

Fig: 1

Fig: 2

Fig 1: AP and Lateral radiographs of the thigh showing displacement oblique femoral mid shaft fracture

Fig 2: After surgery with Ortho-Bridge System (OBS)

Acknowledgement statement

Ethical approval: No

Sources of funding: No

Conflict of interest disclosure: No

Acknowledgements: No

Keywords: Orthopaedics; OBS; Ortho-Bridge System

Received: August 1, 2023; Accepted: August 5, 2023; Published online: December 17, 2023

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10396544>

